

MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract: The digitisation of socio-economic relations against globalisation and market integration trends necessitates fundamentally new strategies for forming marketing approaches to projects activity management. The article aims to analyse project marketing strategies as an adaptive mechanism within the management paradigm in the conditions of the information society. The research employed general scientific methods, including analysis, synthesis, generalisation, abstraction, specification, induction, and deduction. The study analysed a classification of strategic directions for project activities. The specificity of contemporary marketing strategic decisions for mitigating the impact of unstable conditions was considered. The potential for improving the mechanism for forming and optimising marketing approaches to project activity management was substantiated. The need to refine the mechanism of strategic marketing was identified as one of the priority components of an effective management system in the information society. It was proposed that a marketing strategy be developed by profiling according to project management subsystems. The research results have practical significance as they can be applied to develop or optimise marketing strategies in the project activity management system in the conditions of digitisation of societal processes.

Keywords: project management, promotion, strategy, effective development, competitiveness, investor.

1 Introduction

The effectiveness of modern market entities is determined by a complex of marketing measures aimed at forming a targeted strategy for the effective implementation of project activities. The primary goal of project activities is to achieve the operational objectives of the project, which may vary according to the dynamics of its implementation cycle. Innovative management approaches are necessary to achieve these objectives in the rapidly developing information society. In this context, implementing innovative marketing approaches to ensure effective project development while considering exogenous influences becomes relevant. This approach creates optimal conditions for forming a successful algorithm for implementing project activities amidst the digital dynamics of societal processes.

Several current publications focus on researching the development and enhancement of marketing strategies in the context of the information society. Contemporary scholars such as S. Ya. Kasian and D. O. Yuferova (2020) and O. M. Slobodianyuk, O. Yu. Mohylevska, L. V. Romanova and I. Yu. Salkova (2022) investigate the transformation of enterprise project marketing strategies under globalisation. The works of T. Sak (2023) and S. Omelianenko and N. Artiukhova (2021) reflect the aspects of developing a marketing strategy for an enterprise to mitigate the impact of uncertainty in economic conditions. Other researchers (Melnychenko, 2023; Zemko, 2021) have noted that in the context of global digitalisation of societal processes, it is essential to study the mechanisms of preventive risk mitigation in project activities and the elimination of their consequences by making strategic decisions in the project's marketing concept.

Contemporary scholars have thoroughly researched the general issues of strategic marketing in project activity, which require preventing and overcoming related risks (Ruda and Kopytko, 2023). Leading researchers have reflected on specific questions regarding transforming marketing's role as a specific resource in the management paradigm (Koval, 2022; Korohod and Myronenko, 2020). Moreover, scholars emphasise that project marketing continuously evolves in line with the dynamics of a

digitised society, creating optimal conditions for effective business competitiveness.

M. A. Severyn and S. O. Solntsev (2020) consider competitiveness strategies as components of project marketing. However, most of these works describe a fragmented set of tools for developing project management strategies. Therefore, developing a comprehensive approach to forming marketing strategies for managing project strategies in conditions of dynamically increasing competition in the information society is necessary.

2 Literature Review

The works of Ukrainian and foreign scholars have formed the theoretical and methodological basis for developing marketing approaches to project activity management. Many researchers have focused on incorporating marketing technologies into the management process in conditions of intense social informatisation.

Developing project marketing strategies in integrated economic and social conditions against global digitisation has gained significant relevance in contemporary scientific circles. The works of Ukrainian scholars, including M. S. Sadoviyak, L. I. Liubchynskyi, O. V. Bobko, T. S. Tymkevych, and S. R. Tsvyk (2023), primarily focus on the methodology of developing and implementing strategic project marketing, the classification of its mechanisms, and the description of its toolkit. Meanwhile, foreign authors' scientific work (Wang, 2021; Grewal, Hulland, & Koppalle, 2020) has an advantage in proposing a comprehensive practical approach that synergises technical aspects, effective analytics, and adequate assessment to maintain organisational competitiveness.

When considering the role of marketing systems as components of modern project management strategies, researchers R. T. Rust (2020) and B. Özoğlu and A. Topal (2020) affirm the effectiveness and multifactorial impact of targeted tools of innovative digital capabilities on stabilising the process of practical implementation of business projects and advantageous positioning of companies in the market. R. T. Rust (2020) highlights the importance of project marketing in promoting targeted projects in the information society. B. Özoğlu and A. Topal (2020) focus on analysing successful experiences in digital marketing.

Several scholars (Peñalba-Aguirrezabalaga, Sáenz, and Ritala, 2020) believe modern project marketing strategies offer maximum opportunities for practical start-up realisation and innovative project vectors. These strategies also provide preventive protection against potential risks. Researchers suggest that the global pandemic has accelerated the transformational changes towards extensive and rapid digitalisation of society. Organisations that ignore the transformation of marketing projects risk losing significant opportunities.

Verma et al. (2021) have described the basic approaches to implementing strategic project marketing tools and how to increase their effectiveness in terms of competitiveness. However, it is essential to note the practical implementation of marketing tools into project management strategies and their impact on economic activity in the information society. It requires further scientific exploration and detail.

3 Methods that have been applied

The study's methodology was based on various general scientific and specialised methods of cognition. These included abstract-logical, functional, and structural analysis, synthesis, generalisation, specification, induction, deduction, and theoretical modelling.

During the study's implementation, a comprehensive systemic approach was employed to investigate the subject as a system, including its interconnections and interdependencies.

Various analysis and synthesis methods were applied to identify factors in developing the object under study, its defining functional elements, and transformative opportunities for contemporary project marketing strategies. Induction was utilised to implement predictive analysis of the effectiveness of marketing strategies in project management. The project marketing strategy is a structurally consequential system of interconnections formed through the abstraction of conceptual foundations. The generalisation method was used to form priority directions for optimising marketing approaches in the context of the digitalisation of societal processes. project.

4 Research results

Strategic marketing in project management is a modern and relevant concept aimed at supporting the implementation of vectorial improvement and stimulating the effectiveness of economic activity in the era of digitalisation. Marketing approaches in this aspect involve considering opportunities and associated risks arising from the intense digitalisation of socio-economic processes. The marketing strategy is defined as identifying and confirming the goals and tasks of project activities and supporting a range of relationships.

Project management marketing strategies aim to use marketing tools to meet the needs of investors, stakeholders (partners), beneficiaries, and the personal interests of the project manager, as well as current market demand (Rust, 2020; Özoğlu, Topal, 2020).

Modern strategic marketing projects are an integral part of the project management system. They help businesses adapt to market digitisation, support customer loyalty, and stimulate economic efficiency. One of the most significant features of

management that influence the formation of marketing strategies is adaptability to the requirements of information society development and an unconventional approach to their formulation. Additionally, it is crucial to focus on preventive protection and early risk forecasting and implement an effective monitoring and control system over the implementation of marketing approaches. These are created using specific algorithmic actions and response programs for unforeseen circumstances (Verma, Sharma, Deb, and Maitra, 2021). In practice, internal and external strategies are distinguished based on the potential ratio of different components of the project marketing strategy.

Internal project marketing strategies involve optimising the project's financial aspects, positioning it, and highlighting its competitive advantages. External marketing strategies include advancing the project's position, implementing it in projects with large investors, and promoting it aggressively. The choice of strategy priority is determined by the range of influence and the forecast of the development of exogenous and endogenous factors that affect project activity.

Developing and implementing effective marketing methods as components of project management requires the formation of unconventional solutions and the incorporation of innovative methods. In Ukraine's current crisis, it is necessary to rapidly analyse information arrays regarding the impact of negative factors, make swift decisions, and apply particular technologies to ensure the effective implementation of project activities. In addition, selecting a methodology to mitigate the effects of crisis phenomena and prevent them requires minimising potential financial and reputational losses for the enterprise.

Figure 1 displays the algorithm for step-by-step project formation up to implementation. The algorithm presented represents the marketing strategy implementation stages of the project. It visually depicts the logical foundation for the involvement of marketing tools in managing project activities.

Figure 1. Project Marketing Shell

Source: author's conception.

The marketing strategies mentioned in the project management system require further explanation. Specifically, the benefit and cost optimisation strategy involves creating essential factors during project development. These factors enable future investors to achieve maximum benefit and advantage at an optimised project cost.

The project's competitive advantage strategy enhances and complements its benefit strategy. It amplifies the impact of the project's critical success factors. In other words, the project's uniqueness must be maximised and justified compared to its competitive cost. Leadership in uniqueness at an optimal price and focus on the goal provides a more decisive competitive advantage (Peñalba-Aguirrezabalaga, Sáenz, & Ritala, 2020).

The positioning strategy involves establishing clear criteria for identifying and positioning the project as the optimal solution to a given problem. This strategy includes segmenting the project to identify a market niche, focusing on maximum benefit, and ensuring uniqueness and differentiation of risks. The latter point implies enhanced project manageability and mitigation of negative consequences.

External strategies are employed to promote an already developed project. Simultaneously, the aggressive promotion strategy utilises all available project promotion tools, including

those associated with 'unethical marketing' (Sadoviak et al, 2023).

The positional promotion strategy is a method of indirect sales that involves creating hype to enhance the significance of a project. The seller deliberately maintains low activity to generate interest from potential investors, who may then take the initiative to organise the first meeting. This approach is characterised by a waiting period.

The integration strategy for large investors involves positioning additional benefits and advantages for an already active or realised project. The project can complement and multiply the existing effect. This strategy aims to sell the project to a narrow circle of investors.

In a time of increasing digitalisation, the marketing system must conduct a comprehensive risk assessment of project activities, establish an effective plan of regulatory measures, allocate responsibilities, and monitor their implementation. Additionally, the strategy should incorporate an analysis of past marketing mistakes and create a mechanism for preventing their occurrence and minimising their negative impact.

Effective marketing strategies must adapt to the digitised market's dynamic nature and socio-economic development.

Forming these strategies is a crucial stage in the management paradigm, particularly in global digitisation. The assimilation of innovative tools enables integration into the digitised social environment with minimal losses in the shortest possible time.

The project management marketing strategy includes various functional features. These include comprehensive economic activity performance and dynamics analytics, identifying factors that intensify the consequences of crisis phenomena, forecasting, monitoring, and evaluating the internal project potential for localising and mitigating the effects of crisis phenomena. Additionally, the era of digitisation imposes specific

requirements on project marketing strategies. To maintain stability in communication, it is essential to focus on current needs and deliver quality products within shorter timeframes. Moreover, the value of a project often depends on creativity, so it is vital to generate relevant ideas and implement them while considering time constraints. Clear and timely communication is crucial for any marketing strategy, regardless of the duration or strength of a crisis.

Marketing approaches to managing project activities under conditions of intensive digitisation of society have a particular specificity, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Project Marketing Strategy Specifics in the Digital Age
Source: author's conception.

Upon analysing Fig. 2, it is essential to note that Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is a practical implementation of improving project resources in search engine results. It is worth noting that search engine algorithms are constantly changing, which means that the SEO optimisation process requires a permanent specificity (Wang, 2021; Grewal, Hulland, & Kopalle, 2020). Artificial Intelligence in marketing offers the advantage of analysing potential consumers' behavioural responses, leading to an increase in investment return for digital promotion. Implementing chatbots in project marketing improves query processing efficiency, providing quick and specific responses.

In recent years, online events have become a definitive trend in digital marketing. Potential consumers of the project activity product positively perceive the video review format. Social networks and other modern resources provide the functionality for the placement of video content, and the platform interface allows for live broadcasts. It forms the basis for further effective analytics.

The digital marketing trends mentioned above aim to optimise the interaction process with end users through communicative dialogue tools. In marketing approaches to project management, digitisation has impacted the dynamics of fundamental marketing trends and their respective platforms. This impact is expressed through implementing digital marketing tools into the project management paradigm. The potential for additional scientific research appears promising in the context of establishing cost indicators for utilising specific digital marketing tools in practical project management.

5 Discussion

According to researchers (Kalaigianam et al., 2021), adapting the management potential of modern project participants to the requirements of the information society demands a radical shift in marketing approaches. A. Georgescu, M. B. Tudose, and S. Avasilcăi (2023) argue that effective project promotion requires established communication processes with the target audience,

considering the digitisation of societal processes. The authors' view is entirely agreeable.

As convincingly demonstrated by the results of scientific research by contemporary researchers (Barbosa, Saura, & Bennett, 2024), the dynamic adaptation of traditional marketing approaches based on digital optimisation, ensuring effective communication, and leveraging artificial intelligence technologies are necessary components of the process of forming and improving project marketing strategies to create competitive advantages. R. Dušek (2021) suggests that using functional chatbots, mobile applications, and media products can enhance the effectiveness of marketing approaches to managing project activity. It is essential not to ignore this trend.

Several researchers (Rostami & Mirshahi, 2022; Miklosik & Evans, 2020) assure that visualisation is a fundamental requirement of modern marketing processes, guaranteeing effectiveness and versatility across a broad customer audience. Furthermore, according to them, there is a growing need to optimise information systems by implementing integrated software. M. R. Rostami and H. Mirshahi (2022) argue that the effectiveness of a project promotion strategy in a highly competitive environment largely depends on the implementation of the integration process of managing various forms of interaction. Moreover, as scholars assert, information modelling is an analytical and effective tool for processing large volumes of information. The scholars' conclusions align with the findings of this research, demonstrating the necessity for modern project marketing systems to incorporate coordinated data management, automated information exchange operations, timely responses to societal dynamics, and swift adaptation of marketing strategies to new conditions.

Based on the results of scientific research, contemporary researchers (Cluley, Green, & Owen, 2020) have identified the basic requirements for effective transformation of marketing approaches in project implementation management. These include rational use of material and immaterial resources,

minimisation of risks associated with the human factor in information-analytical systems, accessibility for investment, reduction of costs on targeted advertising, and coordination of information flows. Cluley et al. (2020) suggest that implementing this concept can optimally satisfy the project's objective and increase its competitiveness. The authors' findings support the results of the current research.

According to S. Romprasert and A. Trivedi (2021), developing a project marketing strategy should focus on optimising accessibility, completeness, and speed of information retrieval and proposal formation. Researchers argue that it is necessary to implement new interactive means and expand communication boundaries with different categories of end-product consumers. According to scholars, the main principle of project marketing in global digitisation is to ensure effective analytics and market monitoring, consumer trends, and the impact of the socio-economic environment. The concept outlined enables prompt responses to changes and the adaptation of key marketing strategies, forming the basis of a successful management paradigm in project activity.

It should be noted that the number of studies on marketing approaches as components of project activity management remains limited today, with few practical developments. Most works focus on the theoretical aspects of digital transformation, describing algorithms for modelling management processes and methodologies for assessing the effectiveness of the transformation. Further research prospects lie in developing a personalised approach to promoting a project in the market, minimising the risks of non-adaptation to the needs of a digitised society.

6 Conclusions

The effectiveness of marketing approaches to project management in conditions of intensive digitisation of project activities depends on a comprehensive strategy for promoting the project according to the requirements of the information society. The study analysed the potential for optimising marketing approaches to promote projects effectively in the context of global digitisation. It has been demonstrated that utilising innovative opportunities in digitisation within marketing systems can enhance project activities' effectiveness and significantly improve companies' competitiveness. The identified modern marketing tools include optimising communication quality, increasing competitiveness, rapidly adapting project offerings to demand dynamics, and enhancing investment attractiveness. The proposed crisis marketing strategy model reflects interconnected strategic and operational measures subordinated to shared goals and objectives.

The study supports the potential for improving the mechanism of forming and optimising marketing approaches to project management by highlighting the main strategies. It specifies local tactics and mechanisms for their implementation, which constitute a coordinated synergistic system of strategies, methodological support, and practical tools. Therefore, it is clear that improving the mechanism of strategic marketing is a priority component of an effective project management system in the context of an information society.

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Primary Paper Section: A

Secondary Paper Section: AE, AH